

Diversity and Ecology of birds along the selected sites of Sutlej River, Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Aquatic ecosystems provide a vast range of habitats for the aquatic as well as surrounding wildlife. Increased protection of the habitats can ensure the survival of birds and they can gradually adapt to the changing climate. High floral diversity is associated with a higher number of bird species in the area. Aquatic habitats and the associated species are more vulnerable to the risk of anthropogenic activities as compared to terrestrial ones. Identification of bird species, population status, and habitat requirements was carried out in the area from Head Islam to the Bridge of Bahawalpur across the different localities of the Sutlej River. The study of selected sites compiled a total of 51 species belonging to 28 families. Out of 51 species surveyed in the study 2 species Sociable Lapwing (*Vanellus gregarius*) and Indian vulture (*Gyps indicus*) hold the status of “Critically Endangered”, one species Common Pochard “*Aythya ferina*” has “Vulnerable” status while the rest species of birds are “Least Concern” status. The vegetation along the banks of the river is of thorn forest trees and shrubs, while inside the marshy places, aquatic vegetation provides excellent nesting and breeding sites for the water bird species. Maintaining adequate flow of water in the river and vegetation along the river banks is in this regard much important to conserve and protect the avifauna diversity.

Keywords: Birds, Diversity, Habitat, Ecology, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is bordered by Iran and Afghanistan on the west side, while China occupies the north side, whereas India, being our major neighbor, falls on the east side. The land is separated by the Indus River flowing across the country to the south as well as creating the vast Indus Delta, which leads into the Arabian Sea. Pakistan has a wealth of bird habitats from the dry, alpine as well as tropical temperate western Himalayan forests to the Baluchistan as well as Sindh deserts. The Indus basin has also been mostly irrigated and developed and offers a wide range of ecosystems and has been built by some of the earlier human civilizations. Because of its wide range of habitats, a wide range of birds are present in Pakistan. Analysis has shown approximately 669 bird species presence. Above 60 percent of the region, Peshawar has been the Palaearctic by nature, which has forms of steppes and mountain dry habitats on the western as well as the south side of the river Indus and has been varied from the rest Indian sub-continent habitats (Roberts, 1991a; Roberts, 1991b; Grimmett et al., 2008; Mirza, 2012; Ali et al., 2016; Altaf et al., 2018).

The bird fauna of Pakistan is a fascinating combination of Palaearctic as well as Oriental mixing birds which is restricted by the movement of birds to the east and the west side. Since the country attracts visiting birds having some special characteristics. The western part of the Himalayan Bird Fauna is also regarded as a great place to observe, and the western Tragopan is

an example. Pakistan is an important crossroads for the movement of birds. In the autumn and spring, many and many birds pass through Pakistan which mainly goes to and from the Indian subcontinent and also East Africa. Many bird species live in Pakistan throughout the winter season (Grimmett et al., 2008; Umar et al., 2018).

In search of good resources, thousands of birds of many species pass through Pakistan as well as temporarily fly to various lakes and reservoirs in the Indian sub-continent. In the winter seasons per year, Pakistan provides resources for several migratory birds with attractive wetlands. It serves primarily as a central Asian flight route for migratory birds. South-Siberian mountain wetlands are being used as habitats for water birds. The international migrating bird's route number 4 has been projected to migrate about 1 million birds for an approximate distance of 2800 miles. Cranes Teals, Houbara bustards, Geese, Bills of Spoons, Pintails, Mallards, Pelicans, and Waders are mainly birds that migrate from Siberia and Pakistan to the area (Grimmett et al., 2008; Bibi and Ali, 2013; Ali et al., 2016; Umar et al., 2018). The main objectives of the study were to identify the population status and habitats of avian species of selected birds found along the selected sites of Sutlej River, Bahawalpur.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sutlej is known as an important river of the Subcontinent. It passes through the historic crossing area of Punjab. It is to the north of the Vindhya Range, to the south of Himalayan Hindu Kush as well as to the east of Pakistan's Central Suleiman Range. Sutlej River is 550 kilometers long (Figure 1).

Study Sites:

The area from Head Islam to the Bridge of Bahawalpur (National Highway crossing) was selected for random sampling to assess birds' diversity and habitat requirements. The approximate area of research is 120 Km. The whole area was divided into 6 sites for sampling purposes. Moving from the west towards the east the first site was Munshi wali Thokar (National Highway crossing at Sutlej River), Khara Jhoke, 22 Shaheed, Manghwarain, Qasim Di Marri and last Head Islam. The sites were selected based on their accessibility, changes in vegetation and important habitats for conducting research work. During last year (2020) the minimum and maximum: temperature, humidity and rainfall reported from the area are 1.9-45⁰C, 6-100% and 0-1257mm respectively (Regional Agriculture Research Institute, RARI Bahawalpur Metrological Data) as shown in Figure 1.

Data Collection:

A digital camera and Canon Binocular (8x*40x) were used across the different localities of the Sutlej River to assess population status and habitat requirements. Semi-structured interviews and group meetings with local people over the age of 50 years and ornithologists were arranged. Local people having some awareness and knowledge of birds were consulted and reported bird species were listed in the notebook. Birds were identified and matched with the available literature (Roberts, 1991a; Roberts, 1991b; Grimmett et al., 2008; Mirza, 2012). Two visits a week were paid regularly to assess bird diversity from dawn to dusk. The study was conducted from April 2020 to January 2021. We could monitor or report birds that were seen and people informed of their presence in their vicinity. Early morning and late evening the most active period of activity of birds were of prime focus. The expected number of birds at each study site was calculated by taking the average of each species and then obtaining %age abundance.

Relative abundance was calculated by dividing individual numbers of birds counted by the total population of birds of all species at the selected sites of Sutlej River Bahawalpur and multiplied by a hundred.

Percentage abundance = total population of single species/total population of all species x 100

Bird species and their habitat were noted at the adjacent places. The population status and habitat of all the birds were assessed by visual observations and matched with the International Union for Conservation of Nature. The abundance of individuals and species richness at each site was recorded. Different types of bird communities were noted for their existence along the riverside. Species abundance for each sampling point was defined as the total number of species detected during each visit. Abundance for each sampling point was defined as the maximum number of individuals present in the area. Bird surveys were not performed during heavy rains, fog, and during strong winds, since these conditions reduce bird activity, deduction and flawless identification. Species identification was carried out using binoculars and field guides (Grimmett et al., 2008). The questionnaire comprised of following questions: (1) Have you seen this species? (2) How many individuals of the mentioned species are present in the area? (3) What are the habitats of the mentioned species? What are the threats? The indirect data were only collected to verify the direct data.

Figure 1: Map of Sutlej River showing its origination in the Himachal Pradesh region of India and flow towards Pakistan (Map adapted from Google Earth).

RESULTS

The present study about the population status and habitat requirements along the selected sites of Sutlej River Bahawalpur revealed the importance of bird species in maintaining ecological balance. The ten monthly surveys of selected sites compiled a total of 51 species belonging to 28 families. The birds were seen mostly sitting on river banks, vegetation, electricity pools, building structures and in the water of river Sutlej. Families with the number of species in the area are shown in Table 1. Out of 51 species surveyed in the study 2 species Sociable Lapwing (*Vanellus*

gregarius) and Indian vulture (*Gyps indicus*) hold the status of “Critically Endangered”, one species Common Pochard “*Aythya ferina*” has “Vulnerable” status while the rest of species of birds are of “Least Concern” status. The vegetation along the banks of the river is of thorn forest trees and shrubs, while inside the marshy places aquatic vegetation comprising of *Typha augustifolia*, *Saccharum munja*, and many others provides excellent nesting and breeding sites to the water bird species. The following study sites were selected for the research purpose.

1. Munshi Wali Thokar

It is located near the National Highway crossing at Sutlej River. Thirteen bird species were noted from this site. Common myna (*Acridothera tristis*) was 38.2% of the bird species showing maximum population was observed. The minimum population of Indian vulture (*Gyps indicus*)” 0.5% was noted from this study site. The prominent vegetation of this study site is Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*), Frash (*Tamarix aphylla*), Black Siris (*Albizia lebbek*) and Tahli or Sheesham (*Dalbergia sissoo*).

2. Khara Jhoke

21 species of birds were noted from this site. Indian Roller (*Coracias benghalensis*) was 26% of the bird species showing maximum population was observed. The minimum population of Black-rumped woodpecker (*Dinopium bhengalense*) 2.8% were noted from the study site. The prominent vegetation of this study site is Sheesham (*Dalbergia sissoo*), Mango (*Mangifera indica*) and Simal (*Bombyx cieba*).

3. 22 Shaheed

Twenty-four bird species were reported from this site. The maximum population percentage of Red-vented Bulbul (*Pycnonotus cafer*) 41% while the minimum population of Baya Waver (*Ploceus philippinus*) 1.9% is reported in the study area. The prominent vegetation of this site comprised of Sufaida (*Eucalyptus cammaldulensis*), Toot (*Morus alba*), Sukh Chain (*Pongamia pinnata*) and Date Palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*).

4. Manghwarain

Thirty-one species of birds were reported from this study site. The maximum population percentage of White Wagtail (*Motacilla alba*) was 34.95% while the minimum population of Asian Koel (*Eudynamis scolopaceus*) 3.2% was recorded from the study site. The prominent vegetation of the study site includes Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*), Dharek (*Melia azedarach*) and Amaltas (*Cassia fistula*).

5. Qasim Di Marri

It is located away from the Sutlej Pull to the eastward side. Nineteen bird species were recorded from this site. The maximum percentage of House Crow (*Corvus splendens*) was 21.04% while the minimum population of two bird species Bee-eater (*Merops apiaster*) 0.86% and Ring Necked Dove (*Streptopelia decaocto*) 0.75% were recorded from the study site. The prominent vegetation of this site comprises of Jand (*Prosopis cineraria*), Peepal (*Ficus religiosa*), Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*) and Beri (*Zizyphus mauritiana*).

6. Head Islam

It is a structure located on the Sutlej River for water regulation. 42 different bird species were recorded from this study site. The maximum population of Little Egret (*Egretta garzetta*) 39% while the minimum population of Black kite (*Milvus migrans*) 3.2% was recorded from the study site. The prominent vegetation of the site comprised of Kana (*Typha augustifolia*), Sarkanda (*Saccharum munja*), pharagmites and Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Population% age Status of Species in maximum and minimum in the selected study sites.

Figure 3 shows that there is significant variation in the occurrence of different birds in the selected study sites. The maximum percentage of different bird species population in the descending order is 22 Shaheed comprising of Red-vented Bulbul (*Pycnonotus cafer*) 41%, Head Islam maximum population of Little Egret (*Egretta garzetta*) 39%, Munshi Wali Thokar Common myna (*Acridothera tristis*) 38.2%, Manghwarain maximum population percentage of White Wagtail (*Motacilla alba*) 34.95%, Khara Jhoke Indian Roller (*Coracias benghalensis*) 26% was the maximum bird species found in the selected study sites. Whereas, minimum populations of various birds found at the different study sites are at Munshi Wali Thokar Indian vulture (*Gyps indicus*) 0.5%, at Qasim Di Marri Ring Necked Dove (*Streptopelia decaocto*) 0.75%, at 22 Shaheed, Baya Weaver (*Ploceus philippinus*) 1.9%, at Khara Jhoke Black-rumped woodpecker (*Dinopium bhengalense*) 2.8% and at Manghwarain and Head Islam Asian Koel (*Eudynamys scolopaceus*) and Black kite (*Milvus migrans*) 3.2% population of these birds were found respectively.

Figure 4 shows that there is significant variation in the occurrence of different birds in the selected study sites. Maximum number of different bird species in the study area in the descending order is Head Islam 42 bird species, Manghwarain 31 bird species, 22 Shaheed 24 bird species, Khara Jhoke 21 bird species, Qasim Di Marri 19 bird species and Munshi Wali Thokar 13 bird species were reported during the study period. The variation in number of birds is due to several associated factors. The maximum number of bird species was reported by the Head Islam. It is because of the diversity of habitat comprising of species depending on aquatic food, thorn forest vegetation and farmlands. The minimum number of bird species was reported from the Munshi Wali Thokar. It was possibly because of a lack of habitat and traffic noise.

Figure 3: Percentage of species by family in the research area.

Following 51 bird species belonging to 28 different families were identified and reported by the local dwellers about their population status locally, IUCN Red List status and their habitat requirements are mentioned along with them.

1. Family: Cuculidae

The family Cuculidae is represented by two species in the area. These include Asian Koel (*Eudynamys scolopaceus*) and Crow Pheasant (*Centropus sinensis*).

Habitat requirements:

Both species prefer tropical thorn forest vegetation. However Crow Pheasant (*Centropus sinensis*) is seen in the farmlands preferably in the sugarcane fields along the bank of the river.

Population Status:

The population of both species in the area is dependent on the existence of their natural habitat. Asian Koel (*Eudynamis scolopaceus*) is less abundant as compared to the Crow Pheasant (*Centropus sinensis*) according to the native people. According to IUCN Red List, both species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

2. Family: Sturnidae

The family Sturnidae is represented by the two species in the area. These include Bank Myna (*Acridotheres ginginianus*) and Common Myna (*Acridothera tristis*).

Habitat requirements:

These are mostly farmland birds. They are seen foraging around and along the river banks cultivated areas. They build their nests in the sandy banks of rivers, old wells, and holes in old buildings. Both species of bird are abundantly seen in all the habitat types.

Population Status:

The population in the area is increasing according to the local people because of their adaptation to different environments. According to IUCN Red List, both species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

3. Family: Hirundinidae

The family Hirundinidae is represented by the only species of Barn Swallow (*Hirundo rustaca*) in the area.

Habitat requirements:

These are found in all open environment habitats. But in the study area, they frequently built their nests under the bridges and along their walls.

Population Status:

The population of Barn Swallow in the study area is limited to the aquatic habitat providing nesting sites. Their population is generally decreasing according to the local dwellers. According to IUCN Red List, the species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

4. Family: Ploceidae

The family Ploceidae is represented by two species Baya Weaver (*Ploceus philippinus*) and Streaked Weaver (*Ploceus manyar*) in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These are restricted to the marshy habitats and grasses fields along the Sutlej River banks. These built their nests hanging above the water or soil to escape predation.

Population Status:

The population of Baya Waver in the study area is stable. These are adapted to different types of vegetation found in the area. According to IUCN Red List, the species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

5. Family: Meropidae

The family Meropidae is represented by the only species of Bee-eater (*Merops apiaster*) in the study area. These are found along the areas of the Sutlej River.

Habitat requirements:

These prefer freshwater habitats besides being present in thorn forest vegetation and agricultural areas of adjacent vicinity.

Population Status:

According to the local people, the population of Bee-eater is stable in the study area. These are found in all adjacent habitats of the river. According to IUCN Red List, the species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

6. Family: Dicruridae

The family Dicruridae is represented by the species Black Drongo (*Dicrurus macrocercus*) in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These are found in the thorn forest vegetation and agricultural fields around the river banks. These are farmer-friendly birds. These build their nests in the thorn forest vegetation.

Population Status:

According to the local people, their population is decreasing due to the indiscriminate use of pesticides in intensive agriculture production. According to IUCN Red List, the species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

7. Family: Pycnonotidae

The family is represented by four species in the study area. These include Black-headed Bulbul (*Pycnonotus atriceps*), Red-vented Bulbul (*Pycnonotus cafer*), White-Eared Bulbul (*Pycnonotus leucotis*) and White Checked Bulbul (*Pycnonotus leucogenys*). These are considered as farmer-friendly birds.

Habitat requirements:

These are abundantly found in the adjacent agricultural areas of the river. These prefer tropical thorn forest vegetation. These built their nests in the covering of vegetation to hide from predators.

Population Status:

According to the local people population of three species of birds is stable in the study area. According to IUCN Red List, three mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

8. Family: Accipitridae

The family Accipitridae is represented by five species out of which four are of the least concern while one species is of a critically endangered nature. The species comprised of the Black kite (*Milvus migrans*), Black Winged kite (*Elanus caeruleus*), Indian vulture (*Gyps indicus*), Sparrow Hock (*Accipiter nisus*) and Shikra (*Accipiter badius*) in the study area. These mostly include scavengers and birds of prey.

Habitat requirements:

All the species of family Accipitridae habitat in the tropical thorn forest vegetation. They mostly prefer old-growth tree species. However, in the study sites of the adjacent areas of the Sutlej River, these have been seen to build nests in the mobile network towers.

Population Status:

According to the local people, the populations of all species are declining. This is because of the fact of removal of vegetation cover and loss of habitat. Diclofenac Sodium is also a factor in their decline. According to the IUCN Red List Black kite (*Milvus migrans*), Black Winged kite (*Elanus caeruleus*), Sparrow Hock (*Accipiter nisus*) and Shikra (*Accipiter badius*) species hold the status of “Least Concern” while Indian vulture (*Gyps indicus*), hold status of “Critically Endangered”.

9. Family: Motacillidae

The family Motacillidae is represented by three species in the study area. These include Black wagtail (*Motacilla lugens*), White Wagtail (*Motacilla alba*) and Yellow Wagtail (*Motacilla flava*).

Habitat requirements:

These are present in all the habitat types in the study area in agricultural fields, grasslands and desert conditions. These use crevices of buildings and structures for their nesting sites.

Population Status:

The populations of Black wagtail (*Motacilla lugens*), and White Wagtail (*Motacilla alba*) are stable and Yellow Wagtail (*Motacilla flava*) is less abundant in area as compared to the formers. According to IUCN Red List, three mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

10. Family: Recurvirostridae

The family Recurvirostridae is represented by two species Black-winged Stilt (*Himantopus himantopus*) and Pied Avocet (*Recurvirostra avosetta*) in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These prefer marshy, wetlands and pond-like areas. These built their nests on the grasses cover provided by the aquatic vegetation.

Population Status:

The population of Black winged stilt (*Himantopus himantopus*) in the study area according to local people is stable and is found everywhere in marshy habitats. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

11. Family: Ardeidae

The family Ardeidae is represented by three species in the study area. These include Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*), Little Egret (*Egretta garzetta*) and Pond Heron (*Ardeola grayii*). These are considered as farmer-friendly birds.

Habitat requirements:

These three species use thorn forest habitat near the aquatic habitat. Most of the nests are built on trees located on the bank of canals, rivers, ponds, and lakes in the study area.

Population Status:

Their population is fair in all the habitats according to the local people. According to IUCN Red List, three mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

12. Family: Timaliidae

The family Timaliidae is represented by single species of Common Babbler (*Turdoides caudatus*) in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These built their nests in the bushy vegetation of thorn forest vegetation.

These are frequently found in the riparian zone of the Sutlej River. They are also found in the agricultural crops fields looking for insects to feed.

Population Status:

Their population is increasing according to the local people. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

13. Family: Columbidae

The family Columbidae is represented by three species in the study area. These include Common Dove (*Columbina passerina*), Ring Necked Dove (*Streptopelia decaocto*) and Rock Pigeon (*Columba livia*).

Habitat requirements:

These are found along the banks of River Sutlej and agriculture fields in the tropical thorn forest vegetation. These built their nests in bushy vegetation as well as in the crevices and holes in buildings and structures. They feed on grains and seeds mainly.

Population Status:

According to the local people, their population is declining in the study area because of hunting pressure. They were seen in large flocks by the rural people during the harvesting season of grain crops but now a day these are fewer in number. According to IUCN Red List, three mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

14. Family:Upupidae

The family Upupidae is represented by the single species Common Hoopoe or Hudhud “*Upupa epops*” in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These require old decaying thorn forest vegetation and crevices for their nesting sites. These built their nests in the boles of old-grown trees.

Population Status:

Cutting of tropical thorn forest vegetation, particularly Sheesham “*Dalbergia sissoo*” resulted in the decline of their population in the study area according to the local people. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

15. Family: Phasianidae

The family Phasianidae is represented by a single species Common Quail “*Coturnix coturnix*” during this study.

Habitat requirements:

The bird is found along the river banks in agricultural fields and barren areas. These require thorn forest bushy vegetation for nesting under a bushy or in grass cover.

Population Status:

Their population according to the local people is decreasing. The main reason for their decline is the use of excessive pesticides and hunting along with changes in vegetation composition. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

16. Family:Corvidae

The family Corvidae is represented by the single species House Crow “*Corvus splendens*” in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These are found everywhere in all habitats. They have adapted themselves to the changing vegetation and environment. These are omnivorous and so feed on all the available food. These built their nests in the thorn forest vegetation. They prefer to build nests in Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*) trees.

Population Status:

The population in the study area is increasing. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

17. Family:Passeridae

The family Passeridae is represented by a single species of House Sparrow “*Passer domesticus*” in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

These built their nests in the crevices by using straws of grasses and other plants in the old buildings and structures. These are migratory birds. These are seen in large numbers in the study area during the ripening and harvesting season of wheat and Barley crops and do heavy damage to these crops. These feed their young ones the larvae of insects available during the harvesting season.

Population Status:

According to the local people, their population in the study area is declining. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species hold the status of “Least Concern”.

18. Family:Charadriidae

The family Charadriidae is represented by two species during the study period. The species include Red-wattled lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*) and Sociable Lapwing (*Vanellus gregarius*).

Habitat requirements:

Red-wattled lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*) builds their nests on the ground with some stony material and pebbles. These lay their eggs on the pebbles. Sociable Lapwing (*Vanellus gregarius*) built its nest on the ground with grasses and weeds in the close vicinity of human settlements in the study area around the river banks. Due to intensive agriculture around the river banks and trampling by animals, their nests are threatened.

Population Status:

The population of Red-wattled lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*) according to the local dwellers is stable while the population of Sociable Lapwing (*Vanellus gregarius*) is decreasing in the study area. According to the local people, their population in the study area is declining. According to IUCN Red List, the Red-wattled lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*) holds the status of “Least Concern” while Sociable Lapwing (*Vanellus gregarius*) is “Critically endangered”.

19. Family:Coraciidae

The family Coraciidae is represented by one species Indian Roller “*Coracias benghalensis*” in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

It is a secondary cavity nest occupier bird species. It uses the nests built by other birds in the cavities of trees of thorn forest vegetation. The bird is considered farmer-friendly.

Population requirements:

According to the local people, the population of the species in the study area is declining due to loss of habitat and excessive use of pesticides in the intensive farming practices. According to IUCN Red List the Indian Roller “*Coracias benghalensis*” holds the status of “Least Concern”.

20. Family:Alcedinidae

The family Alcedinidae is represented by one species of Kingfisher “*Alcedo atthis*” during this study.

Habitat requirements:

The species builds its nest in the holes in trees of the thorn forest vegetation and dug holes in the ground on the river banks. The bird is dependent on the aquatic habitats for feeding purposes so it nests near the aquatic habitat.

Population Status:

According to the local people the population of Kingfisher has declined in the study area because of decline of water in the river. According to IUCN Red List the species holds status of “Least Concern”.

21. Family: Rallidae

The family Rallidae is represented by one species Moorhen “*Gallinula chloropus*” in the study area. The species is very shy to human being presence in the area.

Habitat requirements:

It requires aquatic marshy habitats for its nesting and breeding. The aquatic vegetation comprising of *Typha augustifolia*, *Saccharum munja*, phragmites and many others provides excellent nesting sites above water to the species.

Population Status:

The species population is declining in the area due to the drying up of marshy places and clearing for agricultural purposes. According to IUCN Red List, the species holds the status of “Least Concern”.

22. Family:Strigidae

The family Strigidae is represented by five species comprising of Common Owl “*Athene noctua*”, Barn Owl (*Tyto alba*), Spotted owl (*Athene brama*), Tawny owl (*Strix aluco*) and Horned owl (*Bubo coromandus*) during the study.

Habitat requirements:

The species use thorn forest vegetation, old abandoned buildings, and abandoned nests are preferably used as nesting sites.

Population Status:

The population of these birds according to the local people is declining due to changes in vegetation composition in the area. Common Owl “*Athene noctua*”, Barn Owl (*Tyto alba*), Spotted owl (*Athene brama*), Tawny owl (*Strix aluco*) population is globally stable while Horned owl (*Bubo coromandus*) is declining globally. According to IUCN Red List all the mentioned species hold status of “Least Concern”.

23. Family:Anatidae

The family Anatidae is represented by the single species Common Pochard “*Aythya ferina*” in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

The species habitat is marshy. Aquatic plants provide nesting and breeding sites to the bird.

Population Status:

The population of bird species is declining due to decline in water flow in the river. It is also globally declining. According to IUCN Red List all the mentioned species hold status of “Vulnerable”.

24. Family: Nectariniidae

The family Nectariniidae is represented by the single species Purple Sunbird “*Cinnyris asiaticus*” in the study area. It is present in the adjacent areas of the river.

Habitat requirements:

It builds nest in the vegetation above ground by using the available grasses and weeds in the area. The adults are seen feeding on nectar of plants and use to feed insects as well as larvae to the young ones.

Population Status:

According to the local people the population of Purple Sunbird "*Cinnyris asiaticus*" is stable. According to IUCN Red List, the mentioned species holds status of "Least Concern".

25. Family: Laniidae

The family Laniidae is represented by one species of long-tailed shrike "*Lanius schach erythronotus*" in the present study.

Habitat requirements:

It is present in all the habitat types. It builds its cup shaped nest in the thorny twigs of thorn forest vegetation by using grasses and straws present around.

Population Status:

According to the local people the population of the long-tailed shrike "*Lanius schach erythronotus*" is stable. According to IUCN Red List the mentioned species holds status of "Least Concern".

26. Family: Scolopacidae

The family is represented by the one species of Common Sandpiper "*Actitis hypoleucos*" in the study area.

Habitat requirements:

It is found at the marshy places. It uses aquatic vegetation of the river and other water bodies in the surroundings for its nesting and breeding.

Population Status:

According to the local dwellers its population has declined due to lower quantities of water flowing in the river. According to IUCN Red List the mentioned species holds status of "Least Concern".

27. Family: Picidae

The family Picidae is represented by one species of Black-Rumped Woodpecker "*Dinopium benghalense*" during the study in the adjacent areas of river banks.

Habitat requirements:

It requires old grown trees of thorn forest vegetation for its cavity nests.

Population Status:

Its population in the study area has been declined according to the local people because of habitat loss. Vegetation composition has been changed and old grown thorn forest species have been cleared for intensive agriculture along the banks of river. According to IUCN Red List the mentioned species holds the status of "Least Concern".

28. Family: Gruidae

The family is represented by two species of migratory birds in the study area. These are Demoiselle Crane (*Anthropoides virgo*) and Common Crane (*Grus grus*).

Habitat requirements:

Both species require marshy areas of Head Islam for their temporary stay here.

Population Status:

The population of both species in the study area has been declined according to the local people because of habitat loss. According to IUCN Red List the mentioned species holds the status of "Least Concern".

It shows that the highest number of species of birds belong to family Accipitridae and Strigidae (10%), followed by the family Pycnonotidae (8%), Ardeidae, Columbidae and Motacillidae (6%), Charadriidae, Cuculidae and Gruidae, Rallidae, Recurvirostridae, Sturnidae(4%) and the rest families comprising of Alcedinidae, Anatidae, Coraciidae, Corvidae, Cuculidae, Dicruridae,

Hirundinidae, Laniidae and Meropidae, Nectariniidae, Ploceidae, Phasianidae, Passeridae, Picidae, Scolopacidae, Timaliidae, Upudidae, occurring in the area are only (2%).

Figure 4: Number of birds of different Species in the selected study sites

DISCUSSION

Water is a basic necessity of life on earth. Rivers are an important source of water across the world. Most of the agriculture in the world is practiced along the river banks. The thorn forest vegetation on both sides of River Sutlej provides excellent nesting and breeding grounds for the different types of birds. Along the river banks are the most fertile agricultural lands which provides an alternate nesting and breeding grounds for the avifauna. Our study matched with the earlier study showing that the most abundant terrestrial birds found along river banks are in similarity to that found along Cauvery river comprising *Corvus splendens* (House Crow), *Acridotheres tristis* (Common Myna), *Cypsiurus balasiensis* (Asian Palm Swift), *Dicrurus macrocercus* (Black Drongo), *Psittacula krameri* (Rose-ringed Parakeet), *Merops orientalis* (Green Bee-eater), and *Turdoides affinis* (Yellow-billed Babbler). Habitat characteristics may affect the avifauna in two different ways. These may be positive or negative. Vegetation composition in this regard plays an important role. Pearce et al. (2007) suggested that along the banks of rivers, the vegetation composition and native flora play an important role in providing suitable to birds for nesting and breeding sites. These riparian sites must be evaluated and criteria for the habitat of various bird species should be set for their conservation. The vegetation of riparian zones acts as a buffer zone. The vegetation composition and anthropogenic activities in the surrounding areas of river greatly influence the diversity and abundance of bird species as indicated in the various studies conducted earlier (Munyenembe et al., 1989), findings indicated that vegetation cover, diameter at breast height, total trees, their height and shrubs height are an important indicator in maintaining adequate diversity of avifauna of riparian zones. These help provide areas for perch, nesting, hiding and seeking food. Vegetation of forests and other land uses is of vital significance for riparian birds and their provision of essential resources given making the sites habitable for the bird communities (Murgui, 2009; Ashraf et al., 2019; Ali et al., 2020). It has been reported by earlier researchers about maintaining adequate vegetation

structure and trees composition for maintaining riparian bird communities (Ali et al., 2018; Altaf et al., 2018; Ashraf et al., 2018; Jadoon et al., 2019; Mughal et al., 2020; Batool et al., 2022).

Table 1: Families with species IUCN status

Sr.	Family Name	Name of Species	IUCN Status
1.	Accipitridae	Black kite (<i>Milvus migrans</i>)	LC
		Black winged kite (<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>)	LC
		Indian vulture (<i>Gyps indicus</i>)	CE
		Sparrow Hock (<i>Accipiter nisus</i>)	LC
		Shikra (<i>Accipiter badius</i>)	LC
2.	Alcedinidae	Kingfisher (<i>Alcedo atthis</i>)	LC
3.	Anatidae	Common Pochard (<i>Aythya ferina</i>)	VU
4.	Ardeidae	Cattle Egret (<i>Babulcus ibis</i>)	LC
		Little Egret (<i>Egretta garzetta</i>)	LC
		Pond Heron (<i>Ardeola grayii</i>)	LC
5.	Coraciidae	Indian Roller (<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>)	LC
6.	Corvidae	House Crow (<i>Corvus splendens</i>)	LC
7.	Charadriidae	Red-wattled Lapwing (<i>Vanellus indicus</i>)	LC
		Sociable Lapwing (<i>Vanellus gregarious</i>)	CE
8.	Columbidae	Common Dove (<i>Columbina passerina</i>)	LC
		Ring-Nicked Dove (<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>)	LC
		Rock Pigeon (<i>Columba liviva</i>)	LC
9.	Cuculidae	Asian Koel (<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>)	LC
		Crow Pheasant (<i>Centropus sinensis</i>)	LC
10.	Dicruridae	Black Drongo (<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>)	LC
11.	Hirundinidae	Barn Swallow (<i>Hirundo rustaca</i>)	LC
12.	Laniidae	Shrike (<i>Lanius scach erythronoyus</i>)	LC
13.	Meropidae	Bee-eater (<i>Merops apiaster</i>)	LC
14.	Motacillidae	Black Wagtail (<i>Motacilla lugens</i>)	LC
		White Wagtail (<i>Motacilla alba</i>)	LC
		Yellow Wagtail (<i>Motacilla flava</i>)	LC
15.	Nectariniidae	Purple Sunbird (<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>)	LC
16.	Ploceidae	Baya Waver (<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>)	LC
17.	Pycnonotidae	Black Head Bulbul (<i>Pycnonotus atriceps</i>)	LC
		Red-Vented Bulbul (<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>)	LC
		White Cheeked Bulbul (<i>Pycnonotus leucogenys</i>)	LC
		White-Eared Bulbul (<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i>)	LC
18.	Phasianidae	Common Quail (<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>)	LC
19.	Passeridae	House Sparrow (<i>Passer domesticus</i>)	LC
20.	Picidae	Woodpecker (<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>)	LC
21.	Rallidae	Moorhen (<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>)	LC
22.	Recurvirostridae	Black Winged Stilt (<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>)	LC
		Pied Avocet (<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>)	LC

23.	Sturnidae	Bank Myna (<i>Acridotheres giginianus</i>)	LC
		Common Myna (<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>)	LC
24.	Strigidae	Common Owl (<i>Athene noctua</i>)	LC
		Barn Owl (<i>Tyto alba</i>)	LC
		Spotted Owl (<i>Athene brama</i>)	LC
		Tawny Owl (<i>Strix aluco</i>)	LC
		Horned Owl (<i>Bubo coromandus</i>)	LC
25.	Scolopacidae	Common Sandpiper (<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>)	LC
26.	Timaliidae	Common Babbler (<i>Turdoides caudatus</i>)	LC
27.	Upupidae	Hudhud (<i>Upupa epops</i>)	LC
28.	Gruidae	Demoiselle Crane (<i>Grus virgo</i>)	LC
		Common Crane (<i>Grus grus</i>)	LC

Key: LC “Least Concern”, VU “Vulnerable”, CE “Critically Endangered”

REFERENCES

- Ali, A., M. Altaf, and M. S. H. Khan. 2016. Winter survey of birds at Keti Bunder, district Thatha, Pakistan. *Punjab Univ. J. Zool* 31:203-208.
- Ali, A., M. S. H. Khan, and M. Altaf. 2018. Winter survey of birds at district of the Badin, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 2(3):11-22.
- Ali, A., M. S. H. Khan, and M. Altaf. 2020. Analysis of anthropogenic activities on avian diversity along the coastal landscape of Sindh, Pakistan *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 4(2):94-110.
- Altaf, M., A. Javid, A. M. Khan, M. Khan, M. Umair, and Z. Ali. 2018. Anthropogenic impact on the distribution of the birds in the tropical thorn forest, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Biodiversity* 11(2):229-236.
- Ashraf, S., S. Kanwal, M. S. Haider, and M. Altaf. 2018. Diversity of birds in rural and urban habitats of district Sargodha, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 2(2):26-36.
- Ashraf, S., A. Riaz, and N. Muhammad. 2019. Assessments of avian diversity of Uchhali lake, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 3(2):8-15.
- Batool, S., T. Mustafa, U. Ali, M. Khan, T. Laraib, and H. Ayoub. 2022. Bird abundance and diversity in vicinity of urban-rural gradient in Khanewal, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 6(4):163-171.
- Bibi, F., and Z. Ali. 2013. Measurement of diversity indices of avian communities at Taunsa Barrage Wildlife Sanctuary, Pakistan. *The Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences* 23(2):469-474.
- Grimmett, R., T. J. Roberts, T. Inskipp, and C. Byers. 2008. *Birds of Pakistan*. A&C Black.
- Jadoon, A., S. Bibi, and A. Rehman. 2019. Birds' population in district Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 3(3):18-25.
- Mirza, Z. 2012. *A field guide to birds of Pakistan*. WWF.
- Mughal, S., M. Pervaz, S. M. Bashir, and S. S. Shamashad. 2020. Assessment of diversity and ethnopharmacological uses of birds in Chakar, Hattian Bala district, Azad Jammu and Kashmir -Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology* 4(1):35-44.
- Munyenymbe, F., J. Harris, J. Hone, and H. Nix. 1989. Determinants of bird populations in an urban area. *Australian Journal of Ecology* 14(4):549-557.
- Murgui, E. 2009. Influence of urban landscape structure on bird fauna: a case study across seasons in the city of Valencia (Spain). *Urban ecosystems* 12(3):249-263.

- Pearce, C. M., M. B. Green, and M. R. Baldwin. 2007. Developing habitat models for waterbirds in urban wetlands: a log-linear approach. *Urban Ecosystems* 10:239-254.
- Roberts, T. 1991a. *The Birds of Pakistan. Non-Passeriformes*. Oxford University Press. Karachi 1:598.
- Roberts, T. J. 1991b. *The Birds of Pakistan: Passeriformes: Pittas to Buntings*. Oxford University Press.
- Umar, M., M. Hussain, G. Murtaza, F. A. Shaheen, and F. Zafar. 2018. Ecological concerns of migratory birds in Pakistan: a review. *Punjab University Journal of Zoology* 33(1):69-76.